
ASSESSMENT OF TEACHER'S PERCEPTION ON ETHICAL AND CIVIC VALUES OBJECTIVES ATTAINMENT IN UPPER BASIC SCHOOLS IN RINGIM EDUCATION ZONE, JIGAWA STATE

By

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Abstract

The study "Assessment of teacher's perception on ethical and civic values objectives attainment in upper basic schools in Ringim education zone, Jigawa state" three objectives were raised in relation to study with three research questions and one research hypothesis s out of which two research questions were answered and one research hypothesis was tested using paired t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The survey research design was employed with four hundred and twenty six (426) were the total population of the study, two hundred and ten (210) samples were selected using cluster sampling techniques. The instrument used for this study was the responses of Junior Secondary School teachers using likert scale questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using SSPS software. The findings for RQ1 revealed that there was a high level of attainment of ethical values in upper basic schools stood at 82.2% while the low level attainment stood at 17.8%. The answer to RQ2 revealed that there was a high level of attainment of civic values at universal upper basic schools in Ringim education zone accounting to 92.3% as against 7.7% the low. With regard to hypotheses tested revealed there is no significant difference between ethical and civic values mean scores at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State, It Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that, teaching and learning ethical and civic values have greatly enhanced the acquisition of such values as honesty, patriotism, civility, obedience, respect to elders and constitutional authorities, self-confidence, self-reliance, self-discipline, kindness and other positives values among upper basic schools of Ringim education zone Jigawa state. It was recommended that teaching of ethical and civic values will be encouraged and emphasized in the study area regardless of school location.

Keywords: Teacher's Perception, Ethical Values, Civic Values, Values Objectives Attainment, Upper Basic Schools, Ringim Education Zone, Jigawa State

Introduction

Education is increasingly acknowledged as the means for combating diverse societal problems. It's also widely attributed as preeminent in fostering attitudes, knowledge and skills of citizens (Birhanu, 2012, cited in Gosa et al., 2014). The education system has a societal responsibility to produce good and responsible citizens, who understand, respect the constitution, democratic values and human rights, develop attitude of research and community service; develop sense of citizenship to participate in and contribute to the development of the community and the country.

Basic education program is referred to a measure which is aimed at addressing inequality in educational opportunity and quality at basic level. Specifically, the program was introduced by the federal government of Nigeria in order to remove distinctions and inconsistencies in the basic education delivery and to reinforce reform Act on education as stated in National policy on education (2004); purposely aimed at rejuvenating the education industry in Nigeria. It's one of the first programs initiated by the Obasanjo led administration in 1999, just after four month of inauguration he made it clear that the scheme would be free and compulsory for every Nigerian child of school going age. Education was a right of every Nigerian child and not a privilege. The basic education is sub divided into three (3) parts as lower basic, middle basic and upper basic. The lower basic is from primary one to primary three (1-3), middle basic covers primary four to primary six (4-6) while upper basic covers junior secondary school one to junior secondary school three (jss1 -jss3). Also, basic education shall be free and compulsory for every Nigerian school age; it shall include mass literacy, education for Nomadic illiterate persons and internal fishermen (NPE, 2013). In 2008 the federal government through the Nigerian Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) develop and introduced the 9 year Basic Curriculum to meet the key target of the UBE Program. Below are general objectives basic educations as;

1. Developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a commitment to its vigorous promotion;
2. The provision of compulsory, free and universal basic education for every Nigerian child school going age;
3. Reducing the incidence of drop-out from formal school system, through improved quality and efficiency;
4. Catering young person who for one reason or the other have had to interrupt their school as well as other out of school children/ adolescent through appropriate forms of complementary approaches to the provision and promotion of basic education;
5. Ensuring the acquisition of an appropriate level of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life skills as well as the ethic, moral and civil values needed for laying a strong foundation for lifelong learning.

Ethical values are principles that guide human behavior and decision making, shaping our interactions with others and world around us. They are essential for building trust, respects and fairness individuals, organization and societies. Embracing these ethical values as honesty, respect, fairness, responsibility, empathy, integrity, transparency, non-maleficence, beneficence, autonomy, justice and care will fosters a culture of trust, respect and social responsibility leading to a better world for all.

Civics values are the principles and beliefs that shape our participation in society, governance and community life. They help us to understand and responsibilities as citizens and promote common good and build a strong, inclusive and engaged citizen. Here are some

the essential civics values patriotism, civic engagement, respect of law and order, tolerance and inclusion, public service, critical thinking, respect of diversity and multiculturalism, environmental stewardship, fiscal responsibility, accountability and transparency, freedom of speech and expression and community involvement.

The ethical and civics values education focused on strengthening student's thinking skills setting the foundation for the free and responsible actions for their individual development and benefit society. Teaching and learning ethical and civics values are of tremendous significant. Currently, an ethical and civics value education is one of the topical issues in the education system its statutory subject to be taught in all educational institutions. The government and the society has to be given emphasis on ethical and civic values education which aimed at making it stand with the purpose of creating citizens that values equality, liberty, justice and democracy that enable to reflect high ethical standard and set the statement in the education and training policy of the country. (MOE, 200 cited in Ashenti sh. 2014)

Attainments of basic education objectives will empowers and provides students with a solid foundation in essential skills and knowledge and to succeed in their personal, social and professional lives, becoming responsible, informed and engaged member of the society. Also the attainment of these objectives will amount to sustainable National development, where children and even adults desire to be educated, read and acquire manipulative and communicative skills for self-reliance.

Upper basic school this is the third level of basic education which a child receives immediately after primary education. As it has been developed by Nigerian Educational Research and Development council (NERDC) in response for effective implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program the upper basic school curriculum was designed to meet the key ideals of the National Economic Empowerment and Development strategies (NEEDs) i.e. Value re-orientation, poverty eradication, jobs creation and wealth generation. Consequently, the upper basic school curriculum was developed to ensure the acquisition of functional education for laying a technical, vocational and entrepreneurship foundations in learners. Consequently, study is to assess the ethical and civic values objectives attainment in upper basic schools in Ringim Education zone, Jigawa State. NPE has come up with the following objectives to be achieved in the upper basic schools as;

- a. Provide the child with diverse basic knowledge and skills for entrepreneurship and educational advancement;
- b. Develop patriotic young people equipped to contribute to social developments and performance of their civic responsibilities;
- c. Inculcate values and raise morally upright individuals capable of independent thinking, and who appreciate the dignity of labor.
- d. Inspire national consciousness and harmonious co-existence irrespective of differences in endowment, religion, color, ethnic and socio economic background; and
- e. Provide the opportunities for the child to develop manipulative skills that will enable the child function effectively in the society within the limit of the child capability (NPE, 2013).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Although ethical and civics values play a significant role in community, however, not well acknowledged and considered as a tool toward stability, agreement and responsible act

of students. The attention given to civics, particularly in the upper basic schools is lower, for instance, civics is being thought by the teachers who graduated non-civics department. Here the school proprietors and school heads allocate or assign someone among the staff regardless of their subject discipline, which of course reduced the quality of teaching.

Ethical and civics values in the study area are collapsing where corruption, embezzlement, armed robbery, kidnapping, wanton destruction of lives and properties, injustice, dishonesty, indiscipline, disrespect to elders and rule of laws, ethnic and religious crises, rape, child/women abuses and trafficking, examination malpractice, drug abuse, cultism, internet and other forms of fraud are the order of the day. I believed that teaching ethical and civics which is moral and social based studies which as problem solving approach to issues and societal problems, if they are properly taught could go a long way to promote good traits such as responsibility, reliability, honesty, obedience, faithfulness, truthfulness, decency and discipline among the students and people at wider society.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to assess UBE objectives on attainment of ethical and civics values in upper basic schools in Ringim education zone Jigawa state. However, the specified objectives of this study are to;

1. To determine the extent at which the Upper basic schools attain ethical values in Ringim education zone
2. To determine the extent at which Upper basic schools attain civic values in Ringim education zone
3. To determine the differences between the ethical and civic values objectives attainment in Ringim education zone.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The researcher develops the following research questions that will be answered by this particular study.

1. What is the extent to which Upper basic schools attain ethical values in Ringim education zone, Jigawa state?
2. What is the extent to which Upper basic schools attain civic values in Ringim education zone, Jigawa state?

Null Hypothesis

One null hypothesis was tested formulated and tested at 0.5 level of significant.

1. There no significant difference in attainment of ethical and civic values objectives in Ringim education zone

Research Design

Survey Research design was employed for this study. It deals with current phenomena spread over a wide area for the purpose of getting clear understanding, control, and subsequent investigation (Olaofe 2010). The design (i.e. survey) helps the researcher to point out the extent of the existing problem or prospect and indicates how such issues could be widespread.

The reason behind employing survey design for this study is the widespread nature of the phenomena under investigation. The study was conducted with aim of “Assessing teacher’s perceptions on attainment of ethical and civic values objectives attainment in upper basic schools in Ringim education zone, Jigawa state.

Population of the study

The total population for this study was four hundred and sixty-five (465) junior secondary school teachers in Ringim education zone, Jigawa state. The table below will show the population distribution of the study area

Table 1: Population distribution of the study in 2 LGEA Ringim education zone Jigawa state.

Ringim Education Zone	Local Education Authority	JSS teachers	Total
	Ringim	249	249
	Taura	216	216
Total		465	465

Source: - MOEST Jigawa state annual school census report 2020

Sample size

Ringim education zone consists of 2 local education authorities Ringim LGEA and Taura LGEA respectively. Therefore, the total sample size was two hundred and ten (210) junior secondary school teachers were randomly selected. This is in line with Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining a sample size.

Table 2 distribution of sample size of the study from Junior Secondary schools in Ringim and Taura LGEAs.

Ringim Education Zones	L.G.E.A. Selected	J.S.S Teachers Sampled	Total
	Ringim	115	115
	Taura	95	95
Total		210	210

Source: - MOEST jigawa state annual school report 2020

Data collection Instrument

A questionnaire for teacher's perception on ethical and civic values objectives attainment in upper basic schools in Ringim education zone jigawa state Nigeria was used. The instrument contained two (2) parts 1 and 2. The part 1 of the instrument was contain the personal information of the respondents which comprises Name of local government education authority, locality, for part 2, section of the instrument was contain sections B to K, containing fifty questionnaire (50) Items with a 4-points Likert scale, indicating Strongly Agree (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) respectively.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The steps carried out in analyzing the data generated from the field work were presented here. The data were summarized via descriptive statistics and presented in frequency distributions. Similarly, the two (2) research questions were answered by descriptive statistics particularly

frequency counts and percentages. However, the one (1) hypothesis formulated was tested via paired sample t-test respectively.

Answers to Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the proportion of the levels to which Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State attain to ethical values?

Levels of Attainment to Ethical Values

Attainment to Ethical Values	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
High	171	82.2	82.2
Low	37	17.8	100.0
Total	208	100.0	

The table above presents the proportion of the levels to which Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State attain to ethical values. The outcomes of the descriptive statistics performed via Statistical Page for Social Sciences (SPSS) revealed that high level of attainment to stood at 82.2% while low level stood at 17.8% respectively. From the results it can be inferred that there is high level of attainment to ethical values in Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State representing 82.2% respectively. The bar chart below further presents the outcome of the analysis.

Research Question Two: What is the proportion of the levels to which Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State attain to civic values?

Table 4.1: Levels of Attainment to Civic Values

Attainment to Ethical Values	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
High	192	92.3	92.3
Low	16	7.7	100.0
Total	208	100.0	

The table above presents the proportion of the levels to which Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State attain to civic values. The outcomes of the descriptive statistics performed via SPSS revealed that high level of attainment to stood at 92.3% while low level stood at 7.7% respectively. From the results it can be inferred that there is high level of attainment to civic values in Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim

Education Zone in Jigawa State representing 92.3% respectively. The bar chart below further presents the outcome of the analysis.

Hypotheses Testing

HO₁: There is no significant difference between ethical and civic values mean scores at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State.

Table 4.2: Paired Sample t-test for Male and Female Ethical Values

Pair	N	Mean	S.D	Std. Error Mean	t-value	Df	P value	Remarks
Ethical Value	208	13.21	3.068	.213				
Civic Value	208	13.36	2.852	.198	.735	207	.463	Not Sig.

A paired sample t-test was performed via SPSS in examining the differences between ethical and civic values objectives attainment at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State. From the table above, in ethical values were having a mean score of 13.21 while the civic values were having a mean score of 13.36 respectively. The computed result from the paired t-test analysis ($t = .735$, $p = .465$, $p > .05$) revealed that the obtained mean scores for ethical values and civic values do not significantly differ. Based on the obtained result, the stated null hypothesis was therefore retained. Thus, it is inferred that a statistically significant difference do not exists in the mean score between ethical and civic values objectives at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State.

Discussion of the Findings

This research was conducted to assess “teacher’s perception on ethical and civics values objectives attainment in upper Basic schools in Ringim Education zone of Jigawa State.

The first finding of this research which stated that there is high level of attainment to ethical values at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State. This is supported by the findings of Tahir (2010) which stated that the attainment of ethical values at Universal Upper Basic Schools is always recommendable as teachers strive their best in facilitating the learners effectively. The researchers also highlights the importance of

ethical and moral values in students and believed that Basic education as a fundamental building block for society and endanger the broader life skills that lead to the social cohesion and provide foundations for vocational callings, higher education and lifelong learning. These when combined will enhanced employment opportunities create a higher level of personal and societal security and development.

The second finding of the study indicated that there is high level of attainment to civic values at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State. This contraindicated the finding of Ukeji (2001) on the attainment of literacy. He stated that the sight of primary school pupils/leavers who don't know how to write letter is "common issue." It's in expressible embarrassment to discover that nine years of schooling has failed to foster this all-important skills in its client (pupils) clearly the state of nation's basic schools is precarious as its degenerating. Something needs to be done to emancipate the educational strata from this self-imposed slavery. Otherwise it will soon be discovered that the certificate we are issuing did not replicate the educational worth of the recipient (graduates). The ethical and civil values are achieved based on the finding of this research. He observed that there is a decline in the quality of basic education and graduates has fallen of attaining educational advancement parameters for instance, lack of communication and literacy competence, poor interaction with others, they failed to understand properly the problem of their society, understand the citizens obligation to make personal contribution equipped with good ethical, civic and democratic culture. This finding is in line with the main objectives of the UBE and also opined by Oguche (2001) who suggested that there is need for enabling law that will promote enrolment, retention in schools and prohibits withdrawal from school for any reason. Furthermore, he suggested that the establishment of Centre for continuing education by every state government. Ayeni (2001) further advocated for a more aggressive public enlightenment campaign for parents at the community level in order to curb cultural attitudes such as early marriage, teenage pregnancy.

The last finding from this study revealed that there is no significant difference between ethical and civic values mean scores at Universal Upper Basic Schools and there is no significant difference between ethical and civic values mean scores at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State. This finding supports the main idea of having no disparity in the provision of education in Nigeria. The finding is also supported by the general objective of the UBE programs which is to education for all. The universal basic education curriculum was designed to meet the key ideals of the National Economic Empowerment and Development strategies (NEEDs) i.e. Value re-orientation, poverty eradication, jobs creation and wealth generation in our children. Thus the 9 year basic education curriculum (BEC) was developed to ensure the ensuring the acquisition of an appropriate level of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life skills as well as the ethical, moral and civil values needed for laying a strong foundation for lifelong learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn.

The first finding of this research which stated that there is high level of attainment to ethical values at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State. The second finding of the study indicated that there is high level of attainment to civic values at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State. The last finding from this study revealed that there is no significant difference between ethical and civic

values mean scores at Universal Upper Basic Schools and there is no significant difference between ethical and civic values mean scores at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone in Jigawa State.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the researcher makes the following recommendations:

1. That teaching of ethical values at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone should be encouraged.
2. That teaching of civic values at Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone should be encouraged.
3. That teaching for the attainment of ethical and civic values should be emphasized in Universal Upper Basic Schools in Ringim Education Zone.

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